

USING MOBILE APPS FOR TEACHING ESL&EFL IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Yuldasheva Saodat Khalmurzayevn

PhD, docent, the department of “Audit”

Toshxonov Mahamadali Turdaliyevich,

PhD, docent, Uzbekistan State World

languages University, The Department of Theoretical Sciences of the Spanish

Language

Yuldashev Sherzod Zairjanovich, *Senior Teacher, Institute of pharmaceutical*

education and research

Abstract. Apps that are not preinstalled are usually available through distribution platforms called app stores. These may operated by the owner of the device's mobile operating system, such as the App Store (iOS) or Google Play Store; by the device manufacturers. We can use mobile apps in teaching language in ESL/EFL classroom.

Key words: *mobile apps, MALL, GPS, application, ESL,*

Introduction

Technology and innovations are always emerging and evolving. New technologies always take over from the old ones. Currently, there is an increasing trend from the use of traditional technologies, such as desktop computers, towards the use of smartphones. Over 70% of learners in developed countries now own and use a mobile phone, while desktop computers enjoy only 40% popularity.

Mobile technology in higher education institutions has made a huge impact. Learning platforms enabled by computing technology, such as online learning, mobile learning, and distance education, provide evidence of the influence of technology in the classroom.

Mobile apps are one of the most significant and important uses of smartphones. The term “mobile” refers mostly to smartphones and tablets; while on the other hand, the term “app” is used as the abbreviated form of “application”.

A mobile application or app is a computer program or software application designed to run on a mobile device such as a phone, tablet, or watch. Mobile applications often stand in contrast to desktop applications which are designed to run on desktop computers, and web applications which run in mobile web browsers rather than directly on the mobile device.¹ Apps were originally intended for productivity assistance such as email, calendar, and contact databases, but the public demand for apps caused rapid expansion into other areas such as mobile games, factory automation, GPS and location-based services, order-tracking, and ticket purchases, so that there are now millions of apps available. Many apps require Internet access. Apps are generally downloaded from app stores, which are a type of digital distribution platforms.

Sometimes, apps are free and you can download from AppStore or Play Market them for free, whereas others need to be paid for, usually at a low cost. Since we are teaching EFL in a higher education setting, we will be exploring my vision of the future classroom through mobile apps in the teaching of ESL in this thesis.

ESL and mobile apps or MALL

Like technology, language learning is always evolving, especially regarding the teaching of ESL/EFL. In the teaching of ESL, mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) is rapidly developing as one of the most applicable domains in technology-supported learning.

According to scientists mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) focuses on the mobility of the learning practice and emphasizes the interaction between the learner and learning content, peers or instructors, which can improve effectiveness, flexibility, and convenience of learning. Furthermore, mobile-assisted language learning helps people to learn a language by using a mobile device.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mobile_app

Mobile devices increase motivation, make the learning process more interesting and enjoyable, and help to improve the skills of the learners in a positive way. Some other benefits of using mobile apps into an ESL classroom are that the mobile apps have a primary impact on the development of the four language skills, including testing.

These apps have quite a significant impact on the development and retention of students' vocabulary. In addition, the language apps also enable students to adopt the practice to their level of knowledge by choosing between apps for beginners, intermediate or advanced learners, and the possibility to assess themselves and monitor their progress.

On the other hand, some of the limitations of the mobile apps in the teaching of ESL are: there is a lack of pedagogical justification while using these apps; sometimes there is a high cost for the device; a lack of human contact, etc. Furthermore, sometimes these language learning apps often provide exercises that test the user without first providing instruction, or they provide only a very few examples of use. In addition, feedback on performance tends to be limited to a checkmark or a cross to indicate whether an answer is correct or incorrect.

Today, there many mobile apps available that can be utilized in ESL classrooms. For example, some of them are Quizlet; Duolingo; English Launch Pad; Culips ESL Podcast; MyWordBook; Speaking pal English tutor; Voxy; Grammar up; English Listening & Speaking; and KAHOOT. Out of all of these ESL mobile

apps, the one we use most frequently in our classes is KAHOOT.

Learning theory that supports the use of mobile apps in the teaching of ESL

One of the learning theories that supports the use of mobile apps in the teaching of ESL is constructivism. According to researchers, constructivist learning is more a matter of going from the inside out. The learner actively imposes organization and meaning on the surrounding environment and constructs knowledge in the process.

Therefore, in mobile app learning in an ESL classroom setting, the learner, through the use of different apps on mobile phones, creates or constructs the language learning process through that learning environment. According to scholars, some of these learning environments should:

Engage learners in activities authentic to the discipline in which they are learning: Therefore, through mobile apps, ESL learners can get engaged in authentic language learning activities.

Provide for collaboration and opportunity to engage multiple perspectives on what is being learned: Here, through the use of mobile apps, ESL learners get lots of opportunities to collaborate with others, such as playing vocabulary games.

Support learners in setting their own goals and regulating their own learning: While learning language through mobile apps, ESL learners are mostly on their own.

Recommendations/conclusion

While exploring some of the mobile apps for our own EFL classes, we have come to the conclusion that there is much to be positive and optimistic about regarding this emerging technology. Therefore, we highly recommend using mobile apps as much as possible.

Since mobile apps are the future of EFL learning/teaching, try utilizing them in the classroom because instructors can enhance their students' vocabulary skills, listening skills, and speaking skills. Mobile apps are very helpful in integrating meaningful cognitive thinking skills in foreign-language learners. Furthermore, mobile apps are very helpful in developing technological skills in language learners. They can enhance reading and writing skills as well.

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